

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	2012	F		Min: 62.9572 Max: 63.7164	5018 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic	Cabri

In cross-section? Yes No
 In elevation drawing? Yes No
 Photos: Yes No #: 2496-2498
 Photo Model: Yes No #: 336

DEFINITION: wall
 Covered by: SU SU
 Fills: SU
 Filled by: SU

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED?
 Color Composition Compaction
 FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
☐ Pottery ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% ☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)
 Northern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Southern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Western Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Eastern Limit: Original Not Original Excavation Limit
 Depth: Original Not Original

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abuted by: SU 1058	Abuts:
Is covered by: SU 0	Covers: 1245
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
 After opening trench F, the extent of this wall is much better visible

DESCRIPTION
 Position within sector: eastern edge of Trench F
 Shape: linear

For layers complete this section:
 Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions):
 Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
 Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
 Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:
 Cut edges: rounded straight
 Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
 Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
 How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
 How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
 Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

1394
00/1100
via Claudia

wall 1245
wall 5018
SU 5016
construction cut 5017
5004
(rubble fill, very loose)

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

NW-SE

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify) basalt

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material

Tufa Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size

Small (range) Medium (range) Large (range) Representative size, e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

29 high x 25 wide x 28 height

134 cm length

49 height

width ~38 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

length 7.80m height 62 cm (max) width 45 cm (max)

Description:

bottom ashlar blocks, some with some fill + small rocks between them. Upper rocks are more crumbly tufa, smaller in size, with less square edges. Two possible drainage cuts that have been filled in later

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Two types of tufa are present. The grey tufa could be disintegrated ashlars. Some orange tufa ashlars have also been used. Wall is characterized by soil and small rocks between many stones used.

<p>SOIL SAMPLING: ☐ Yes ☒ No</p> <p>Total volume of layer (buckets):</p> <p>Sample quantity (buckets):</p> <p>Sample fraction (%):</p>	<p>NON SOIL SAMPLES: ☐ Yes ☒ No</p> <p>If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):</p> <p>Size:</p>	<p>SIEVING: ☐ Yes ☒ No</p> <p>Total volume of layer (buckets):</p> <p>Sample quantity (buckets):</p> <p>Sample fraction (%):</p>
<p>STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY</p> <p>☐ Good ☒ Fair ☐ Poor</p>	<p>Filled-out by: LWS</p> <p>Revised by: CHM</p> <p>PDFd by: GP</p> <p>Entered by:</p>	<p>on: July 2 2012</p> <p>on: 11.7.2012</p> <p>on: 12.7.2012</p> <p>on:</p>